

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

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New healthy products / Recipes from the first batch of selected varieties validated in WP3

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the set of healthy products and recipes co-created in some of the living labs of the DIVINFOOD project from the first batch of varieties of neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs) selected during the first period of the project. This deliverable thus also highlights mild processes that can be implemented with NUCs. It compiles a number of experiments and tests carried out in the LLs to introduce NUCs into innovative or renewed recipes/products. These experiments were carried out by or in collaboration with local food SMEs (small-scale processors, collective catering, commercial restaurants), along a co-creation perspective.

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1. Introduction

In the face of environmental challenges and the many issues they raise, the sustainability of food systems depends largely of changes in diets. One of the main objectives of the DIVINFOOD project is to reintroduce NUCs into diets by co-creating products and recipes that promote more vegetarian diets and protein diversification, while relying on more sustainable agricultural production models and mild processing techniques. These NUCs offer significant nutritional benefits at reasonable prices.

This document presents the products and recipes that have been co-created with the first batch of selected varieties validated in the WP3 of the project.

Methodology

The products and recipes are categorised as follows: the products are offered by sellers (retailers, farmers selling directly, etc.) and include both foods that require additional preparation (e.g., pasta, bulgur, etc.) and ready-to-eat foods (e.g., dairy-like yogurt). Under recipes, we have categorised everything that can be prepared by a chef and served in a restaurant or in collective catering.

For the products table it was decided to highlight the following parameters:

- The name of the NUC
- The product resulting from mild processing (bulgur, flour, etc...)
- How it was produced (major steps of the mild processing)
- The difficulties that may be encountered during the process
- Recommendations for processing it
- The level of innovation and the adaptation to specific diets (e.g., vegetarian, vegan)
- The shelf life and storage recommendation
- How the product can be used

The recipes have been divided into 3 categories:

- Home-made recipes, generally easy to cook and reasonably priced
- Recipes for mass catering, easy to prepare in large quantities and at a reasonable price. We have also included in this category recipes that make use of cereals and legumes beyond the simple role of accompaniment.
- Recipes for chefs and restaurants, which include the most difficult and meticulous recipes (seasoning and preparation) and which can also be more expensive.

For the recipes table it was decided to highlight the following parameters:

- The name of recipe
- The NUC used
- The categories of dish and the adaptation to specific diets
- The ingredients in grams and litres
- The steps of preparation
- The novelty of the recipe (innovative or renewed from a traditional recipe)
- The level of difficulty between easy, medium or hard

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- The time of preparation
- The cost with scale: at € the dish is principally composed of vegetable ingredients, at €€ the dish is composed with meat or cheese, at €€€ the dish is composed with more meat or cheese and with rare ingredients like saffron or truffle.
- The number of people for whom the recipe is intended
- The necessary tools

For the recipes in catering and in restaurants we listed:

- The potential allergens, because for restaurants and catering it is an obligation to prevent sanitary risks.

For collective catering we tried to document two additional pieces of information:

- Nutritional assessment. However, it was difficult to complete this information because the tools used to make the nutritional assessment do not document the nutritional value of NUCs because there is no interest in these neglected crops.
- The storage and reheating conditions but it was also complicated to get this information because the recipe first needs to be tested with a catering chef in real conditions.

This documented list of recipes and products is a first step that can be updated and will be used to support the preparation of future deliverables of the WP2.

During the 36 first months of the project, 11 products and 26 recipes were co-created in DIVINFOOD LLs with the first batch of varieties selected in the WP3. These products and recipes are classified in 4 categories, following what was planned in the DoA (see table 1).

Categories of products/recipes	LLs involved in co-creation
Innovative products using fermentation	LL GPea-Port LL Leg-ItSwitz
Mixed legumes-cereal products	LL GPea-Port Leg-ItSwitz LL Cer-Occ
New cereal-based products	LL Cer-Occ
Legumes-based new recipes	LL Bean-Lyon LL Bean-Cast LL Leg-Nord

Table 1. Categories of products and recipes co-created in DIVINFOOD Living labs.

The change of personnel at BioCivam 11 has delayed the drafting of the deliverable by one month. This delay has no impact on the rest of the project. Moreover, the participatory documentation of the co-created products and recipes provided a lot of elements for the future deliverable on the guidelines to develop new products/recipes from mild processing (D2.2).

2. List of the first batch of selected varieties validated in WP3

The different varieties used to co-create new products and recipes were validated and approved by the DIVINFOOD partners in month 12 of the project (Milestone No. 7). All the varieties listed in the table 1 are being tested and produced in the different LLs. This work is being carried out in a participatory manner, involving a variety of local stakeholders. Each LL is characterised by different dynamics, whether technical, technological or organisational, but also by different activities (seed multiplication, on-farm cultivation, breeding, processing and cooking). This contributes to explain the differences in the mild processing tests carried out in each LL.

Name of the NUC	Description (Source: Deliverable 3.1)	Varieties (source: Milestone 7)	In which LL varieties were tested for products and recipes
Meat Bean	"Haricot Viande" was usually cultivated in the French Alps (Chartreuse and Oisan mountains) during the first half of the XXth century. In 2017, just one farmer family cultivated it for their own consumption. It had nearly disappeared. Thanks to a local association (Semences en Montagne), this bean has been saved.	There is only one variety called 'Meat-Bean'	LL Bean-Lyon
Lingot bean	Lingot bean is a small white oval bean with curved appearance. It has a tender and thin outer skin with a soft, creamy texture and a rich, buttery flavour. It requires no pre-soaking and cooks tender in an hour with a guaranteed softness.	Several varieties are being tested and multiplied, but at the moment there isn't enough production to test products and recipes. These have therefore been made with the closest and best known variety, "Hidalgo".	LL Bean-Cast
White Lupin	White lupin is a legume whose grain and seed have gained increasing interest but it is a different botanical species to narrow-leaved (Lupinus angustifolius). It has recognized nutritional properties, namely a high content of proteins, dietary fibres and low fat content.	Lupinus albus "Frieda" Lupinus Albus "breeding line 1 by Fibl"	LL Leg-ItSwitz
Grass Pea	Grass pea is a traditional legume from Portugal, apart from other Mediterranean countries - where the seeds are typically white - and also from some Asian countries - where the seeds are typically dark. This crop is very resilient, being very resistant to dry climate, drought but also flood and to some fungal diseases. Seeds used in these mild processings were obtained from Alvaiázere farmers.	Lathyrus sativus "small"	LL Gpea-Port
Einkorn	The name einkorn ("single seed" in German), is derived from the presence of a single grain in each spike or from the husk	Triticum monococcum "36"	LL Cer-Occ

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	<p>surrounding the grain. Einkorn, which was already cultivated about 12,000 years ago, is known as the ancestor of wheat, originating from the Fertile Crescent region. It is mostly produced in marginal areas and adapted to poor soil and it has regained importance regarding sustainable agriculture and nutritional values.</p> <p>Einkorn is generally produced in poor soils. It is not very sensible to drought. It grows under Mediterranean climate or continental climate. It is a very adaptable crop able to grow in salty, flooded or drought conditions</p>	<p>Triticum monococcum "47" Triticum monococcum "48" Triticum monococcum "55" Triticum monococcum "56" Triticum monococcum "67" Triticum monococcum "68" Triticum monococcum "69" Triticum monococcum "80" Antenato IGP Haute-Provence</p>	
Rivet wheat	<p>Rivet wheat - also named Poulard, Cone or English wheat - is a free-threshing tetraploid winter cereal, which was differentiated throughout the Neolithic era from other descendants of domesticated emmer (Triticum dicoccum) like Durum, Polish, Khorasan and Persian wheat.</p>	<p>Poulard d'Auvergne</p>	<p>LL Cer-Occ</p>
Lentil	<p>Lentil is a cool season legume crop belonging to the Fabaceae family. It is an excellent food source to provide energy, proteins and iron in the human diet. Lentil is an annual herb, erect in growth form, much branched with a slender stem. Agronomic requirements for lentil differ from region to region depending on the climatic conditions, cropping system, and variety.</p>	<p>Gotlandslins (lentil) Anicia (lentil) Beluga (lentil) Rosana (lentil)</p>	<p>LL Leg-Nord</p>
Grey Pea	<p>The grey pea has historically been a staple for northerners, but has been phased out and completely lost ground in Sweden from the 19th century till today. Grey pea was used in everything from soups to bread and it has even been said that each parish in Sweden had its own grey pea variety before it was phased out as the yellow and green peas were refined and gave better yields.</p>	<p>Rättviksärt (grey pea)</p>	<p>LL Leg-Nord</p>

3. Implication of stakeholders into the co-creation of products and recipes

One of the key objectives of DIVINFOOD is to encourage and promote participatory approaches involving local stakeholders. As part of this initiative, the LLs involved in the task 2.1. have mobilised SMEs, training organisms and associations working on food processing. These include: processors who have either tested the performance of these NUCs for the first time or have already been actively involved in their use; culinary laboratories working on the development of mild processes to improve the nutritional value and taste of NUCs; and restaurants introducing NUCs into the menus of their establishments, or interested to do that, whether private restaurants or collective catering.

The table below lists the different local stakeholders that participated in the project in the concerned LLs. This is followed by a brief description of the stakeholders by LL. Five of these stakeholders are also members of the consortium (EIP Purpan affiliated to INRAE, Nordisk Ravara, CookingLab, Institut Lyfe (ex-IPBR), CREA) while other members of the consortium acted as facilitators (FIRAB in LL Leg-ItSwitz, UNL in LL GPea-Port, BioCivam 11 in LL Bean-Cast and LL Cer-Occ).

Type of stakeholders	In LL Bean-Lyon	In LL Bean-Cast	In LL Cer-Occ	In LL Leg-ItSwitz	In LL Gpea-Port	In LL Leg-Nord	Total
Private Restaurant	1						1
Collective catering	1	1					2
Medium processor - seller			1			1	2
Small processor - seller	2			1			3
Culinary laboratory					1		1
Training / research organism		1	1	1			3
Food shop				1			1
							13

3.1 Description of stakeholders in LL Bean-Lyon

- **Small canning factory (SME)**

This canning factory has been working on putting meat beans in jars, in particular to make them easier to use them in recipes (pre-cooking).

- **Small processor – Miller (SME)**

Artisan miller who processes meat beans into flour, to help the use of this NUCs into recipes. This company is equipped with modern tools to preserve maximum nutritional quality during mild processing.

- **Private restaurant (SME)**

Gastronomic restaurant with a long-standing commitment to sustainable sourcing.

- **Collective catering establishment (association)**

Administrative restaurant committed for a long time to a ‘responsible canteen approach’.

3.2 Description of stakeholders in LL Bean-Cast

- **Collective catering establishment**

Canteen of an agricultural college, in which the chef cooks to introduce future farmers to NUCs

- **Institut Lyfe (ex-IPBR) (research and training organism) (DIVINFOOD partner)**

Institut Lyfe (ex-IPBR) conducts multidisciplinary research on food and hospitality questions in relation to pleasure and health. They worked in particular to co-create recipes for vegetarian cassoulet and developed new recipes with lingot bean.

3.3 Description of stakeholders in LL Cer-Occ

- **EIPurpan (training organism) (INRAE’s affiliated party, DIVINFOOD partner)**

The participation of EIPurpan in the task 2.1 was not mentioned in the DoA but is essential to support the co-creation of new products in the LL Cer-Occ. For instance, the mild processing of einkorn into bulgur required laboratory tests of various parameters before continuing the tests in real conditions. This was an opportunity to involve students in the tests, making them aware of the issues of NUCs mild processing.

- **Medium-scale agri-food cooperative (SME)**

This collective of farmers, millers and consumers has developed a supply chain for neglected cereals by reintroducing old species (Einkorn and Rivet Wheat). This initiative existed before DIVINFOOD and continues to develop. As part of the project, this SME takes part in the co-creation of new products with einkorn and rivet wheat.

3.4 Description of stakeholders in LL Leg-ItSwitz

- **Company selling organic products collaborating with food processors (SME)**

This specialised organic food retailer with a well-known brand sells its own brand food products to specialised shops and supermarket chains, as well as online. It mainly works with plant-based organic food for health-conscious consumers looking for innovative products. It has hundreds of food products in its portfolio, some of which are based on the NUC.

- **Micro company specialised in fermented foods (SME)**

Specialised in fermented foods, this company processes organic ingredients to get miso and other fermented foods. It recently bought a farm to grow its own ingredients and mostly works with legumes. It sells online and to specialised shops. The company owner promotes fermented foods through workshops and dissemination initiatives.

- **CREA (research organism) (DIVINFOOD partner)**

Leading Italian research organization dedicated to the agri-food supply chains.

3.5 Description of stakeholders in LL GPea-Port

- **Cooking Lab – R&D Laboratory (SME) (DIVINFOOD partner)**

At GPea-Port, the products and food recipes were developed by the DIVINFOOD partner CookingLab, a R&D SME dedicated to the development of science based innovative foods and beverages (mainly fermented products) and processes, more sustainable and healthy.

3.6 Description of stakeholders in LL Leg-Nord

- **Nordisk Ravara (SME) (DIVINFOOD partner)**

Medium-scale food company collaborating with local organic growers of legumes, and developing food products and recipes.

4. Innovative products using fermentation

4.1 Innovative products created in the LL GPea-Port

NUC	Products from Mild processing	How it was created (major steps)	Results	Difficulties	Recommendations	Necessary tools	Level of innovation and adaptation to diet	Shelf life and storage recommendation	How to use it
Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Sweet grass pea Miso	Definition of a manufacturing diagram; experimental trials to establish of standard production conditions for the grass pea miso (incubation time and temperature; salt concentration; Aspergillus oryzae spores' concentration); selection and test of selected yeast starter cultures. Chemical and physical analysis; Antioxidant properties analysis. Consumer acceptance tests.	Creation of a new formulation with a functional diagram and lower salt concentration, grass pea miso paste judged to have a better taste than soybean miso paste	Impurities in seed lots	Legumes should be cooked until a soft texture was obtained	weight scale, bowl, pressure cooker, stove, blender or pestle, measure spoons, glass bottle with close lid	Adaptation of ancient eastern methodologies and reduction of salt concentration; establishment of standard production conditions for the grass pea (incubation time and temperature; reduction of salt concentration; Aspergillus oryzae spores' concentration). Adaptation of previous typical recipes and uses for soy bean miso to be used with Alvaiázere region typical legume (grass pea).	No need for thermal treatment (e.g. pasteurization) nor refrigeration. While in non-opened recipients, miso paste has a shelf life from 6 months to more than 1 year. After opening, food safety is kept if recovered with a layer of salt and closed. Along preservation, colour evolves to darker pigments without safety issues involved. Storage conditions: closed recipients, room temperature.	(1) As paste to make Miso soup, (2) seasoning/flavour agent with strong umami flavour, (3) colorant for caramel pigment, (4) ingredient rich in proteins and antioxidants
Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Salty grass pea Miso	Definition of a manufacturing diagram; experimental trials to establish of standard production conditions for the grass pea miso (incubation time and temperature; salt concentration; Aspergillus oryzae spores' concentration); selection and test of selected yeast starter cultures. Chemical and physical analysis; Antioxidant	Creation of a new formulation with a functional diagram, grass pea miso paste judged to have a better taste than soybean miso paste	Impurities on seed batches	Legumes should be cooked until a soft texture was obtained	weight scale, bowl, pressure cooker, stove, blender or pestle, measure spoons, glass bottle	Adaptation of ancient eastern methodologies; establishment of standard production conditions for the grass pea (incubation time and temperature; salt concentration; Aspergillus oryzae spores' concentration); use of selected starter cultures. Adaptation of previous typical recipes and uses for soybean miso to be used with Alvaiázere region typical legume (grass pea).	No need for thermal treatment (e.g. pasteurization) nor refrigeration. While in non-opened recipients, miso paste has a shelf life longer than 1 year. After opening, food safety is kept if recovered with a layer of salt and closed. Along preservation, colour evolves to darker pigments without safety issues involved.	(1) As paste to make Miso soup, (2) seasoning/flavour agent with strong umami and salty flavour, (3) colorant for caramel pigment, (4) ingredient rich in proteins and antioxidants

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		properties analysis. Consumer acceptance tests.				with close lid		Storage conditions: closed recipients, room temperature	
Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Grass pea Tempeh	Definition of a manufacturing diagram; experimental trials to establish of standard conditions for grass pea tempeh production (pulse cook level; incubation time and temperature; Rhizopus oligosporus spores' concentration, size of the batch production; initial acidification); Chemical and physical analysis; Consumer acceptance tests	Creation of a new formulation with a functional diagram, grass pea tempeh judged to have a better taste than soybean tempeh.	Impurities on seed batches, holes from Bruchus wheevel	Legumes should not be cooked to softness; cooked grains should not be too wet.	Cup, bowl, pan, stove, measure spoons, incubator, kitchen paper, 0.5-1L plastic bags, sharp fork, grid	Adaptation of ancient Indonesian processes; establishment of standard production conditions for the grass pea tempeh (degree of softness, incubation time and temperature; Rhizopus oligosporus spores' concentration; size of the batches). Adaptation of previous typical recipes and uses for soybean miso to be used with Alvaiázere region typical legume (grass pea).	Must be cooked or frozen after preparation. If not cooked immediately, it must be frozen or kept in the refrigerator: Refrigerator: 2-3 days Freezer: 1-2 months.	(1) as meat substitute in hamburgers, stews, meat balls, and others (2) rich protein flour, (3) tempeh chips and snacks

4.2 Innovative products created in the LL Leg-ItSwitz

NB. These products have been developed with a commercialised lupin flour of which the variety/varieties are not indicated, while awaiting flours of varieties cultivated in the LL.

NUC	Products from Mild processing	How it was created (major steps)	Results	Difficulties	Recommendations	Necessary tools	Level of innovation and adaptation to diet	Shelf life and storage recommendation	How to use it
white lupin Lupinus albus	dairy-like yogurt	the lupine flour was reconstituted at 10% with water and subjected to fermentation with commercial lactic ferments for yogurt	Fermentation was easily achieved but the texture of the product was not compliant with an yogurt-like product	a critical separation of whey and solid component after fermentation, so the product was not homogeneous	Partial substitution of water with milk		a plant-based yogurt totally from white lupin does not exist yet	not available	to drink
white lupin Lupinus albus	yogurt enriched with lupin flour	the lupine flour was reconstituted with and partially with milk, then subjected to fermentation with commercial lactic ferments for yogurt	Fermentation was easily achieved but the texture of the product was still not comparable with yogurt	still visible a critical separation of whey and solid component after fermentation.	Inclusion of texturizing lactic acid bacteria to improve the		a plant-based yogurt totally from white lupin does not exist yet	not available	to drink
white lupin Lupinus albus	dairy-like cheese	50% pasteurized skim milk:50% pasteurized lupin flour dissolved in water (10%). Thermo-acid coagulation. The obtained curd is pressed to remove excess liquid	The product was similar to a ricotta cheese with still a bitter taste	Enzymatic coagulation did not occur. To reduce the bitter taste	Use also salt or additives like sunflower oil or potato starch or aroma to improve the texture and the taste		Meet a flexitarian diet. Try to perform a new kind of cheeses reducing the quantity of cow milk, without using soya.	not available	to eat or to spread

4.3 Recipes which have been tested with these fermented innovative products

4.3.1 Recipes to make at home

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Steps of preparation	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€, €€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Grass pea Salty Miso soup	Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Starter; vegetarian (vegan, gluten-free)	- 2 tbsp grass pea salty miso paste - 4 cups vegetable broth or water (1L) - ½ cup diced tofu - leek (finely sliced)	-Heat the water but do not let it boil. -Dissolve miso paste in a small bowl of warm water, then add the rest of the water. -Add tofu. Simmer gently for 2-3 minutes. -Serve hot in a bowl, garnished with green leek finely sliced.	Easy - innovative	10	€	4	electric kettle or pot; knife, bowls, kitchen board
Grass pea Tempeh chips	Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Side dish; vegetarian (vegan, gluten-free)	- grass pea tempeh	-Cut the tempeh like French fries -Fry (semi-dip) in hot oil -Serve accompanied by a small bowl of slightly diluted grass pea salty miso, for dipping and seasoning.	Easy - innovative	15	€		frying pan or air-dryer

4.3.2 Recipes to make in catering

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Potential allergies	Nutritive value estimation	Steps of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Prawn balls with grass pea salty miso	Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	starter; flexitarian	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 285g prawn crumb - 30g grass pea salty miso - 15g finely chopped leek - Zest of 1 lemon - A few drops of lemon juice - 1 egg - 10g breadcrumbs - Breadcrumbs to coat the prawn balls 	seafood; contains gluten		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Preheat the oven to 180°C. -Place the prawns, miso, leek, lemon zest and juice and egg in a food processor and process for 15 seconds at medium speed. -Add the breadcrumbs and mix well. -Shape into small balls, flatten and roll in the breadcrumbs. -Place the prawn balls on a baking tray lined with greaseproof paper and bake at 180°C until golden brown, about 10 minutes. Alternatively, you can fry the balls in oil or in the air-fryer. 	Medium - innovative	30	€€	5	Food processor, bowl, knife, weight scale, grater, lemon juicer
Grass pea salty miso mayonnaise	Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Sauce; gluten-free	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 250g oil - 1 egg - 5mL lemon juice - 15g grass pea salty miso 	egg		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add the egg, lemon juice and miso to the blender jar and blend for 1.5 minutes at medium-low speed. While blending, pour the oil little by little until getting mayonnaise consistency. 	Easy - innovative	5	€€	270g	Food processor, weight scale, lemon juicer

4.3.3 Recipes to make in restaurants

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients	Potential allergies	Steps of preparation	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Grass pea Salty miso mayonaise	Grass Pea Lathyrus sativus	Sauce; Vegetarian (vegan), gluten-free	-150g of oil -15mL lemon juice (1/2 lemon) -15mL of water -15g grass pea salty miso -2g soy lecithin (1%) -0.4g xanthan gum (0.2%)	soy	- Weigh the oil and set aside. - Add the lemon juice, water, miso and lecithin to the blender jar and mix well. - With the blender running, add the oil little by little (the emulsion will be stable but a little liquid). - Add the xanthan gum and mix again with the blender. - Serve as desire.	Medium - innovative	20	€€	180g	Food processor, weight scale, lemon juicer
Grass pea sweet miso mousse	Grass pea Lathyrus sativus	Dessert side dish; gluten-free	- 400mL pasteurised cream - 40g sugar - 2 vanilla pods - 15g grass pea sweet miso (2 charges of nitrous oxide for the siphon)	milk, vanilla	Heat the cream in a saucepan. -Split the vanilla pods open lengthways with a knife, scrape out the inside and add to the cream along with the open pods. -Bring to the boil, lower the heat to minimum and add the miso and sugar. Mix well. -Leave to infuse for about 15 minutes. Pass the mixture through a sieve and place in a gas siphon. Leave to cool in the fridge for about 15 minutes. -Add a charge of nitrous oxide and stir well. Serve.	Easy - innovative	60	€€€	25	weight scale, knife, sieve, gas siphon

5. Mixed legumes and cereals products

NB. These products have been developed with a commercialised lupin flour of which the variety/varieties are not indicated, while awaiting flours of varieties cultivated in the LL Leg-ItSwitz.

NUC	Products from Mild processing	How it was created (major steps)	Results	Difficulties	Recommendations	Necessary tools	Level of innovation and adaptation to diet	Shelf life and storage recommendation	How to use it
White lupin Lupinus albus	Gluten-free lemon bisco lupino	Whisk the ingredients (vegetable cream, sugar, vanilla and salt) in a mixer. Add the eggs and lemon cream and continue beating. Add the flours (lupin, rice, maize), previously mixed by hand or at first speed. Roll out with a rectangular pastry roller (to reduce production waste), cut into squares, Bake at 175° in a static oven for about 12 minutes, then lower to 150° for another 8 minutes.	biscuits ready for consumption	skilled baker for good assemblage		kneading machine with dipping arms, oven	Renewed vegan	a few weeks	As biscuits

6. New cereal-based products

NUC / varieties tested	Products from Mild processing	How it was created (major steps)	Results	Difficulties	Recommendations	Necessary tools	Level of innovation and adaptation to diet	Shelf life and storage recommendation	How to use it
Rivet wheat (Poulard d’Auvergne) and Einkorn (IGP Haute-Provence) Triticum turgidum and Triticum monococcum	Bulgur	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sorted and dehulled einkorn or rivet wheat - Cleaning and Sorting - Soaking (1 kg of wheat for 2kg of water. 3h30, 55°C) - Precooking (45 minutes, 100°C, Humidity 40%) - Drying (15h30, 60 to 20°C, 10% humidity) - Crushing - Classification / Sieving (1 to 2 mm) = Bulgur 	Creation of a new recipe with a functional diagram, products judged to have a better taste than the commercial bran	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impurities in the batch because of a bad sorting - Already crushed einkorn presented risks of mold and of agglomeration 	Keep a little amount of hulled grain in order to clean the stone mill during milling	Sorting machine, dehuller, mill	<p>Innovative (not yet produced on a small-scale)</p> <p>Easily digestible. Not gluten free but consumed by gluten intolerant (non-coeliac) consumers. Contains antioxidant and all amino acids.</p>	Shelf life shorter than classic wheat flour.	Like traditional Bulgur

7. Legumes-based new recipes

7.1 Recipes from the LL Bean-Lyon

7.1.1 Recipes to make at home

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Coleslaw with mayonnaise meat bean base	"meat bean" ("haricot viande") Phaseolus vulgaris	Starter (vegetarian)	Ingredients Cooked meat beans 500 g Shallots 100 g Mustard 100 g Oil 30 cl Vinegar 6 cl Salt pepper	Mix shallots finely, add mustard, vinegar and cooked meat beans. Add the oil and adjust the seasoning. Add chopped parsley or basil according to your taste. Make a Coleslaw by grating Carrots: 500 g Green cabbage 500 gr. Mix together with the meat bean mayonnaise.	Easy - innovative	25 minutes (once meat beans cooked)	€	4 or 6	blender
Fish and meat bean rilette	"meat bean" ("haricot viande") Phaseolus vulgaris	dish or starter	Ingredients for about 500g : Meat beans 200 g Sardines in oil (or other fatty fish) 200 g Shallots 40 g Lemon juice 2 to 4 cl	Finely blend meat beans, lemon, cream, shallots. Crush the flesh of the sardines and mix together	Easy - innovative	15 minutes (once meat beans cooked)	€	4 or 6	blender

7.1.2 Recipes to make in catering

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	potential allergies	Nutritive value estimation	Steps of preparation	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €€,€€,€€ €)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Meat bean and lamb in hash parmentier	meat bean Phaseolus vulgaris	main dish	0.030 litres organic milk 0,011 kg Fine salt 0.001 kg Ground white pepper 0.050 U Sariette 0,010 kg Grease gun 1,500 kg lamb shoulder 0,400 kg meat beans 0,500 U Rosemary 0,015 kg Sweet butter from a lump 5kg 0,030 kg Local yellow onion 0,030 kg Carrots washed 0.001 kg Fennel seeds 0.020 kg Garlic from a bag of 5kg 0,200 L White table wine Protected geographical indication	milk	Nutritional values per serving (297g): Energy : 343 kcal Protein : 42 g Lipids : 18 g Carbohydrates : 2 g Fibre : 0,3 g Iron : 2,7 mg Without the calculation of the intake of the meat bean currently. Waiting for analysis data	Soak beans in a large volume of water for 12 hours. Soak beans in a large volume of water for 12 hours. Cook beans with cold start until boiling Total cooking time: 2 hours Drain and mix the beans with the butter and milk until you get the consistency. Keep warm. Season the lamb, then bake in a mixed oven 130*20% for 3 hours. When out of the oven, scrape it and mix with the degreased juice. Arrange 130g of lamb in a circle and 110g of mashed beans, then juice and fresh grass. Add fried beans to decorate.	Medium - renewed	Soak beans in a large volume of water for 12 hours. beans cooking time: 2 hours Lamb cooking: 3 hours.	€€	10	Pan, sauce pan, blender

7.1.3 Recipes to make in restaurants

recipe	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients	Potential allergies	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
<p>Stew of meat bean, Smoked Vegetable Garnish and Wild Mushrooms from with Savagnin wine. Maison TETEDOIE, Chef Christian Têtedoie & Chef Chrisitophe Carlier</p>	<p>meat bean Phaseolus vulgaris</p>	Main dish	<p>Beans meat 400 g Wood mushrooms, chanterelle grise, girolle, trumpet, sheep's feet Echalote 2 pieces Butternut squash or pumpkin 1 small</p> <p>Savagnin PM Chives 1 Bundle Parsley 1/4 of a bundle Butter 70 g Garlic 1 clove Salt plate PM Hay 1 handle Mustard 1 teaspoon mocha</p> <p>Meat beans: 400 gr meat beans 1 carrots 1 onions 1 shallots 1 clove of garlic 2 l vegetable broth 1 sprig of thyme QS salt</p>		<p>Soak the beans overnight the night before. Prepare the bouquet garni and the aromatic filling. Start cooking beans in vegetable broth, add the aromatic filling 1 carrots, 1 onion, 1 shallots, 1 clove of garlic, 2 l vegetable broth, 1 sprig of thyme. In three-quarters of cooking, salt the recipe. Cook the recipe gently. Drain the meat beans, filter and preserve and add the butter, Add a little strong old-fashioned mustard. Add the Savagnin and chives at the last moment. Correct if needed.</p> <p>Cook the mushrooms. In a skillet, melt the butter with a clove of garlic. Add the mushrooms when the butter is frothy. Add the chopped shallot and chives after seasoning.</p>	Medium - renewed	<p>Preparation for beans cooking 10 minutes Beans cooking approximately 2 hours to 2 hours 30 minutes depending on the power of the "fire". Preparation for vegetables: 30 minutes cooking 20 minutes</p>	€€	4	Pan & sauce pan

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					<p>For the squash, cook on salt about 1 hour. To smoke, peel and cut into pieces. Put on a hole plate or rack and under the hay. Smoke and close for 3 to 5 minutes. Proceed with the preparation of the plate.</p>					
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7.2 Recipes created in the LL Bean-Cast

7.2.1 Recipes to make at home

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Chili sin carne with lingot bean	Lingot bean Phaseolus vulgaris	Main dish (Vegetarian)	<p>Chilli :</p> <p>Lingot bean : 200g Peeled tomatoes : 380 g Firm tofu : 200 g Onion : 200 g Carrot : 100 g Red pepper : 30 g Green pepper : 80 g Celery : 70 g Brown sugar : 12 g Water : 12,5 cl Garlic : 2 cloves Cumin in powder 3 g Salt and pepper</p> <p>Dressing :</p> <p>Fresh cilantro : 4 strand Avocado : 2 Green lemon : 2 Tacos : 8 : Green chilli : 1</p>	<p>Place the beans in a large pan, fill with 1.5 litres of water. Bring to a boil. Skim from time to time and cook for 1h30.</p> <p>Peel and chop the onion, garlic, red chilli, carrots, celery and peppers</p> <p>Stir fry onions and the garlic for about 2 minutes. Add the carrots celery and pepper. Let cook for 5 minutes.</p> <p>Add the red pepper, cumin and brown sugar. Let cook for one minute while skimming</p> <p>Dice the tofu and tomatoes and add them with the beans to the preparation.</p> <p>Add enough water so that the mixture is humid and boil and let cook for about 10 minutes</p> <p>Cut the avocados and green chilli into strips.</p> <p>Brown the tacos in the pan.</p> <p>Put the chilli in the centre of the tacos with a few slices of fresh avocado, a slice of lime and cilantro leaves</p>	Easy - renewed	75 minutes	€€	4	Pan

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Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Steps of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Cassoulet Carne	Lingot bean Phaseolus vulgaris	Main dish	Lingot Bean : 400g pork belly Bio : 300g Toulouse sausage Bio : 4kg Duck leg : 2kg Saidoux : 1kg thyme : a pinch Ail : a pinch Romarin : a pinch salt : 400g White base* : 1,5 L Bouquet garni : a pinch Carrot : 200g Onion : 300g Rind : 300g Salty bacon : 2g gralic : 1g	<p>lingot bean :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Soak for 12 hours in water 2. Drain 3. Put the beans in cold water 4. Bring to a boil for 5 minutes 5. Drain <p>Duck confit:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Salt the duck 1 hour 2. Rinse 3. Confit in the oven at 120°C for 2 hours <p>Toulouse Sausage:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brown the sausages in a stove <p>Pork belly:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. brown the chicken breast in a pan <p>Cooking lingot beans:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cook the beans in the white base for 1 hour 2. Drain and keep the broth <p>Montage:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Line the bottom of the casserole with the pieces of rind 2. Add 1/3 of the beans 3. Arrange the meats 4. Put the salted pork and the garlic 5. Add the remaining beans 6. Arrange the sausages on top, sunk halfway 7. Pour the broth 8. Pepper the top and add a spoonful of lard soup that was used to brown the meats 9. Bake at 150°C for 2 hours, breaking the crust several times <p>Reheat: The next day, reheat at 150°C for 1 hour and 30 minutes</p>	Medium - renewed	240 minutes	€€€	4	Pan

7.2.2 Recipes to make in catering

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	potential allergies	Nutritive value estimation	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Pana Cotta	Lingot Bean Phaseolus vulgaris	Desert	For Panacotta Ligot bean 375 gram Milk 525 gram Sugar 90 gram PectinX58 7 gram pomegranate coulis pomegranate jus 600 gram Sugar 40gram PectinX58 12 gram	Milk	Grammage portion (1 pers.) : 163 g Coût portion (1 pers.) : 0.19 € Valeurs nutritionnelles moyennes portion : - Protéines :5.22g - Lipides : 0.98g (dont acides gras saturés : 0.53g) - Glucides :25.78g (dont sucres : 20.45g) - Energie : 132.80 Kcal,555.10 Kj - P / L :5.35 - Calcium :112.58mg - Sel :135.36mg	Lingot bean: 1. Soak the beans in water for 12 hours 2. Drain 3. Cook in boiling water for 1 hour and 30 minutes Pana Cotta: 1. Continue cooking the beans in the milk sweeten for 30 minutes 2. Mix the whole thing 3. Switch to Chinese 4. Heat to 80°C 5. Add the pectin and sugar 6. Modling in glassware pomegranate coulis : 1. Heat the pomegranate juice 2. Add the sugar and pectin 3. Bring to a boil for 2 minutes 4. Clear the grenade	Medium - innovative	60 minutes	€	10	Pan, Mixer, Sieve

7.2.3 Recipes to make in restaurants

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients	Potential allergies	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Vegetarian Cassoulet	Lingot bean Phaseolus vulgaris	Main dish (Vegetarian)	Ingredients : Lingot bean : 400g Artichoke : 3 Dry ceps : 300g Mushroom broth : Bouquet garni : 1 Carrot : 200g Onions : 300g Mushroom : 1 kg Water : 1L Maizena		Put the beans (that have been soak for 12h before) into cold water and bring to simmer. Prepare the broth by heating the bouquet garni. Then add the mushrooms. Wet and let simmer for 30 minutes. Mix and add maizena. Cook the beans into the broth for one hour. Drain and keep the broth Rince the ceps and cut the artichokes in quarter. Assemble the Cassoulet : put one third of the beans in the cassole (a kind of plate). Put the artichokes and the ceps. Add the rest of the beans. Cool at 150°C for 2h. Brake the crust multiple times during the cooking.	hard - renewed	240 minutes	€€	4	Pan
Saffron Lingot bean soup and summer vegetable minestron	Lingot bean Phaseolus vulgaris	starter / Main dish (vegetarian)	Saffron Broth : Lingot bean : 200g Bouquet garni : 1 White onion : 200 g Roasted Garlic: 100 g Cream : 400 g Basil: 250 g Garnish of beans: Carrots : 150g Red pepper : 150g Yellow pepper : 150g Zucchini : 150g Olive oil : 30g Salt : 3g		Saffron broth : Cook the beans for 1h in boiling water Sweat in olive oil the bouquet garni, chopped onions, chopped garlic and beans Add water and let simmer for 1h Remove the bouquet garni Roost the garlic in the oven at 200°C in aluminium foil. Infuse Basil a few minutes and season with salt and pepper. Garnish of beans : Cook the beans 1h in boiling water. Cut all vegetables in brunoises Sauté the vegetables in olive oil to cook them lightly. Season with salt and pepper and add basil.	Medium - Innovative	210 minutes	€€	10	Pan, oven

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			Pepper: 1g Basil		Assembly : Put the garnish in the middle of a plate in a circle and add some broth.					
Croquetas bean, goat cheese, espelette pepper	Lingot bean Phaseolus vulgaris	starter / Main dish (vegetarian)	Bean puree : Lingot bean : 1kg Cream : 100g salt : 4g pepper : 1g Chive : 1/4 bunch Goat Cheese : fresh goat cheese : 500g Espelette Pepper : 5g salt : 2g Breadcrumbs: flour eggs breadcrumb salt Frying Oil 2L		Bean puree : 1. Cook in boiling water for 1h30 2. Drain 5. Blend the beans with the cream, salt, and the pepper 3. Pass through a sieve to get a puree smooth 4. Cool 8. Add the chopped chives Insert goat cheese: 1. Season the goat cheese with the chilli pepper Espelette and salt 2. Mould into small spheres and freeze Breadcrumbs: 1. Put the insert in a ball of mashed potatoes of bean 2. To roll in flour 3. Dip in the beaten egg 4. Bread with breadcrumbs 5. Fry in oil at 160°C for 2 minutes	hard - Innovative	90 minutes	€	10	Pan, Mixer, Sieve fryer, round mould

7.3 Recipes created in the LL Leg-Nord

7.3.1 Recipes to make at home

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€ €)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Rattvik pea hummus	Rattvik pea	Starter (vegetarian)	Rattvik pea 250g Water 0,230L Lemon juice 39g Tahini 13g Pressed Garlic 6,5g Salt 6,5g Cumin 3g Cold pressed rapeseed oil 13g Parsley 13g	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rinse the peas thoroughly. 2. Soak the peas in 1.5% salted water for about 8 hours. (1.5% salt corresponds to about 2 tsp/litre) 3. Strain the water and boil the peas in plenty of water for about 15-20 4. Let the peas cool in their own broth and then pour off the husk. 5. Squeeze lemon juice 6. Press the garlic. 7. Weigh all ingredients and process in a food processor or with a hand blender until smooth consistency. (Peas, rapeseed oil, water, lemon juice, garlic, tahini, cumin and 8. Top with cold-pressed rapeseed oil and finely chopped parsley 	Easy - renewed	30 minutes	€	10	, Knife, cutting board, plate for serving pan
Legume Pickles	Gotland lens, Green Lens Anicia and Autum tail Lens Culinaris	Starter or Main dish (Vegan)	Gotland lens 100g Autum tail 100g Green Lens 100g Red onion 50g Carrot 50g Lemon zest 10g Star anise A pinch Bay leaf A pinch Carnation a pinch Vinegar 0,1L sugar 180g Water 0,3L	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Make a 1-2-3 layer by mixing vinegar, sugar and Water 2. Soak Autum Lentils, Gotland Lentils and Anicialins and cook according to instructions. Let cool. 3. Rinse and peel/zest organic lemons. 4. Mix the cooked legumes with 123-team, lemon zest and all the spices. 5. Let steep for a couple of days for best results. 	Easy – renewed	15 minutes	€	10	Knife, cutting board, plate for serving pan

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Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €€€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Pasta sauce on Gotland lentils	Gotland lentils Lens Culinaris	Main Dish (vegan)	Gotland lens 200g Water 0,75L Crushed tomatoes 600g Yellow onion 250g Carrot peeled 100g Parsnips 50g Tomato puree 50g Rapeseed oil 50g Cooking wine 50g Basil 20g Sambal Oelek 20g Garlic peeled 10g Vegetable broth 10g Salt 5g Thyme 2,5g Oregano 2,5g Black pepper 1g	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rinse the lentils thoroughly 2. Soak the lentils in 1.5% salted water for about 8 hours. (1.5% salt corresponds to about 2 tsp/litre) 3. Strain the water and rinse the lentils in 4. Grate the peeled carrots and parsnips 5. Weigh all ingredients and check against the recipe. 6. Sauté the yellow onion, garlic, carrot, parsnip and tomato puree with rapeseed oil until it starts to soften. 7. Pour in the cooking wine and stir for a few minutes. 8. Pour in water and Gotland lentils, let boil for a few minutes 9. Pour in crushed tomatoes, sambal oelek, thyme, oregano and black pepper 10. Cook to desired consistency 11. Mix lightly with a hand blender to get a better result 12. Season with basil, vegetable broth and salt. 	Easy - renewed	30 minutes	€	10	, Knife, cutting board, frying pan, plate for serving
Sandwich With Gotland lentils, fresh herbs and tomato	The Gotland Lentil (PDO) Lens Culinaris	Vegan, Vegetarian, principal dish or starter	8 slices of light sourdough bread (about 1.5cm) 800g boiled Gotland lentils 2 large steak tomatoes 1 cardamom salad 8 tablespoons of olive oil Sea salt Black pepper Herb mayonnaise : 250g vegan mayonnaise 20g chervil 20g chives 20 g coriander 20 g parsley 15 g lemon juice	<p>DO THIS 1. Rinse and dry the herbs. Save a little until it accumulates. Mix them smoothly with mayonnaise and lemon. Season with salt and black pepper. 2. Turn the cooked lentils into the herb mayonnaise. Season with salt and black pepper. 3. Slice the tomatoes, about 1 cm. 4. Shred the cardamom salad, about 0.5 cm. Rinse and dry. 5. Fry the bread slices in olive oil until they are golden brown.</p> <p>SERVING Place the shredded lettuce on the sandwich. Then add the tomato slice and the lentil salad. Finish with fresh herbs, sea salt and black pepper, as well as a few drops of olive oil.</p>	Easy - renewed	About 10 minutes	€	8 servings	Blender, Knife, cutting board, frying pan, plate for serving

7.3.2 Recipes to make in catering

Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	potential allergies	Nutritive value estimation	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : € ,€€ ,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Lentil Pakora	Gotland Lentil Lens Culinaris	Main dish (Vegan)	Lentil 450g Potatoes 600g Red onion 450g Cauliflower Organic 450g Chili 30g Salt 24g Turmeric 12g Fresh coriander 10g Cumin 6g Frying oil			1. Rinse and soak the lentils for at least 4 hours then Strain and rinse the lentils. 2. Blend the lentils with a little bit of water and spices to a paste. At first, coarsely grind but i will loosen and become smoother the longer is mixed. Is should be complete smooth. 3. Mix the lentil batter with sliced onion, sliced potato, chopped chilli, cauliflower florets and chopped fresh coriander. 4. Heat the oil to 150°C and fry vegetable balls of about 65g. 5. Alternatively, fry in grassed baking tray in the oven on high heat with dry air or on frying pan.	Medium - renewed	30 minutes	€	10	knife cutting board saucepan Oven strainer measuring jug frying pan
Spread on anicia and basil	Green lens anicia Lens Culinaris	Starter (Vegan)	Green Lens anicia 550g Rapeseed Oil 28g Water 0,28l Basil 19g Lemon juice 3g Salt 1,5g Pilled Garlic a pinch			1. Rinse the lentils thoroughly. 2. Soak the lentils in 1.5% salted water for about 8 hours. (1.5% salt corresponds to about 2 tsp/litre 3. Strain the water and boil the lentils carefully in plenty of water for about 1- 4. Let the lentils cool in their own broth for about 5 minutes and then pour off the broth. 5. Let the lentils cool completely. 6. Squeeze lemon juice 7. Peel the garlic. 8. Weigh all ingredients and check against the recipe. 9. Heat the rapeseed oil to +60°C if you want a greener color. 10. Mix the basil with the warm rapeseed oil. 11. Add the remaining ingredients and mix until smooth. 12. Serve as a sandwich spread with all types of bread or as a stir-fry for the main course at the salad buffet	Easy - renewed	30 minutes	€	10	knife cutting board saucepan strainer measuring pan

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Recipes	NUC	Categories of the dish and diet	Ingredients (gram, litre)	potential allergies	Nutritive value estimation	Step of preparation	Level of difficulty – Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Spread on Korallins and roasted carrot	Korallins rosana Lens Culinaris	Starter (Vegan)	Korallins Rosana 70g Carrot 50g Water 0,04L Rapeseed oil 28g Lemon juice 3,5g Gralic 3g Salt a pinch			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rinse the lentils thoroughly. 2. Soak the lentils in 1.5% salted water for about 8 hours. (1.5% salt corresponds to about 2 tsp/liter 3. Strain the water and boil the lentils in plenty of water for about 1-2 4. Let the lentils cool in their own broth for 5 minutes and then pour off the water. 5. Let the lentils cool completely. 6. Peel and slice the carrot. 7. Peel the garlic. 8. Squeeze lemon juice 9. Weigh all ingredients and check against the recipe. 10. Confit the carrot and garlic with the oil in a saucepan until the carrot is soft and then cool completely. (NB save the oil for mixing 11. Blend all ingredients until smooth. 12. Serve as a sandwich spread with all types of bread or as a stir-fry for the main course at the salad buffet 	Easy - renewed	45 minutes	€	10	knife cutting board saucepan Blender strainer measuring pan
Lasagna With Gotland lentils	The Gotland Lentil (PDO) Lens Culinaris	Vegetarian main dish	Pasta sauce on Gotland lentils Boiled Gotland lentils 4 kg Water 7.5 L Crushed tomatoes 6 kg Peeled yellow onion 2.5 kg Parsnip 500 g Tomato puree 500 g Rapeseed oil 500 g Cooking wine 500 g Basil (frozen) 200 g Sambal Oelek 200 g Garlic (peeled) 100 g Vegetable broth 100 g Salt 50 g Thyme 25 g Oregano 25 g Black pepper 10 g Bechamel sauce Oat milk 19kg Flour 625 g Rapeseed			<p>Pasta sauce on Gotland lentils</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Grate the pre-peeled carrots and parsnips. 2. Weigh all the ingredients and match the recipe. 3. Sauté yellow onion, garlic, carrot, parsnip and tomato puree with rapeseed oil until it begins to soften. 4. Pour in the cooking wine and stir for a few minutes. 5. Pour in water and boiled Gotland lentils, let boil for a few minutes. 6. Pour in crushed tomatoes, sambal oelek, thyme, oregano and black pepper. 7. Cook to desired consistency. 8. Mix around a little lightly with an immersion blender to get a better consistency. 9. Season with basil, vegetable stock and salt. <p>Béchamel sauce</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pour oil and flour into a saucepan over medium heat, stir with a 	Medium - renewed	75 minutes	€€	100 servings	knife cutting board saucepan oven dish grater kitchen scale Blender strainer measuring jug frying pan

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		oil 565 g Vegetable broth 65 g Salt 62.5 g Nutmeg (ground) 12.5 g White pepper (ground) 12.5 g Other Lasagna plates 4.5 kg Grated cheese 2.2 kg Tomato (sliced) 5 kg			<p>whisk.</p> <p>2. Pour in oat milk, a little at a time while stirring to avoid lumps.</p> <p>3. Bring the sauce to a boil while stirring.</p> <p>4. Season with nutmeg, white pepper, broth and salt.</p> <p>5. Strain the béchamel sauce if necessary.</p> <p>Lasagna</p> <p>1. Build the lasagna by layering in tin with béchamel sauce at the bottom, lasagna plates, lentil sauce, béchamel sauce, lasagna plates, etc.</p> <p>2. Top with grated cheese and sliced tomato.</p> <p>3. Bake in an oven at 140°C until golden and the pasta is soft</p>					
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7.3.3 Recipes to make in restaurants

recipe	NUC	Ingredients	Potential allergies	Step of preparation	Categories of the dish and diet	Level of difficulty - Level of innovation (innovative or renewed)	Time of preparation (minutes)	Cost (Scale : €,€,€,€€€)	Number of people	Necessary tools
Beluga lentil Bowl with garlic mash	Beluga lens Lens Culinaris	For Beluga lens Bol : Beluga lens 350g Carrot 400g Beetroot 400g Onion 400g Caper 100g Red Wine vinegar 35g Tarragon 20g For Garlic Mash : Potatoes 1,4kg Oat Milk 500g Butter 100g Garlic (cooked) 20g Garlic (fresh) 8g Salt 10g White pepper 4g Nutmeg 1g		Beluga lens Bowl : 1. Rinse the lentils thoroughly and cook according to the instructions on the package. 2. Mix diced carrot, chopped red onion and beetroot with oil and roast in the oven at 200°C. until they have a nice color and soften a little with chewing gum 3. Chop tarragon and pour in vinegar. 4. Mix the roasted carrot, red onion and beetroot with the lentils, capers, vinegar and fresh chopped tarragon. Garlic Mash : 5. Peel and boil potatoes until soft. 6. Peel and cook garlic with oat milk, butter, white pepper and grated nutmeg. 7. Grate fresh garlic and set aside. 8. Mash the boiled potatoes and garlic and mix with the oat milk mixture. 9. Season with freshly grated garlic and salt.	Main dish (Vegetarian)	Medium - renewed	45 minutes	€	10	

8. Conclusion

The next deliverables to be produced in relation to this deliverable are a guideline for the development of new products/recipes from mild processing (D2.2, M48) and new healthy products/recipes from the second batch of selected varieties validated in WP3 (D2.6, M60). Deliverable D2.2 will be based on the experience gained during the co-creation process.

This initial work has shown that NUCs can be used and processed in a variety of ways and that a large number of products and recipes can be renewed or invented to make our plates more plant-based, diversify our protein sources and make our food more sustainable.